

About the project

Critical thinking about technology is a key aspect of computing education. Given the multifaceted role of computing in climate change, it is increasingly important to support children in thinking about connections between sustainability and technology within school curricula. However, there is currently a lack of knowledge about whether and how these links are taught in practice, and conversely, how to best support teachers to teach them.

Through this project, we've sought to map curricular links between sustainability and computing in the Scottish curriculum; engage with teachers to understand gaps and challenges in how these links are, and could be, taught; and develop this guide to help teachers reflect on how they could identify and teach these links in relation to the Scottish Curriculum for Excellence.

To do this, we engaged with teachers in diverse communities and geographies in Scotland. By focusing on diverse teaching experiences we sought to ensure that the research represents a range of voices, developing collective knowledge as to how sustainable computing education can feasibly be implemented in schools.

The research has been developed through a partnership between the Institute for Design Informatics, University of Edinburgh and Ostrero, a small business which supports sustainable communities in Scotland through circular economy work and education.

About this guide

Based on our research – which involved reviewing literature alongside interviews and design workshops with teachers – we identified three ‘puzzle pieces’ that we suggest can be used to help ideation of sustainable computing lesson plans.

The first is the list of **UN Sustainable Development Goals** [1], which we found all teachers in our research to already be familiar with. The second is the Scottish **Curriculum for Excellence Technologies Experiences and Outcomes** [2]. We identified these as a natural fit to teaching about sustainable computing, although we note that there are also relevant Experiences and Outcomes in other curriculum areas, particularly related to data literacy, that could be relevant to explore (see [3] for an overview). The final puzzle piece is three overarching broad topics based on **competencies that we see important for children and young people to develop** in order to support thinking about sustainable computing. These are: Understanding life cycles of computing technologies; Thinking about the energy impact of computing technologies; and Using computing to take action on the environment and climate.

In this guide we provide three examples of lesson topic ideas that combine these puzzle pieces, alongside guiding questions that can be used to develop classroom activities. We see these as being flexible to adapt to different key stages and ages. We also provide a blank puzzle canvas that teachers can fill out to ideate other lesson topics.

If you would like to find out more about this work please get in touch!

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References

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- [1] <https://sdgs.un.org/goals>
 - [2] <https://education.gov.scot/curriculum-for-excellence/curriculum-areas/technologies/>
 - [3] <https://dataschools.education/resource/experiences-and-outcomes/>
 - [4] <https://www.gov.scot/publications/making-things-last-circular-economy-strategy-scotland/>
 - [5] <https://unctad.org/publication/digital-economy-report-2024>
 - [6] <https://information-services.ed.ac.uk/iot/soprano-project>

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